

EXTENT OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF BUSINESS PERMITS AND LICENSING SYSTEM IN SELECTED CITIES IN LAGUNA: BASIS FOR SYSTEM ENHANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the implementation of the Business Permits and Licensing System (BPLS) in San Pablo City, Calamba City, and Santa Rosa City, Laguna. Employing a descriptive research design, the study gathered data through a survey questionnaire distributed to employees of the Business Permits and Licensing Office (BPLO) in the selected cities. Descriptive statistics, such as mean ($\bar{x}$) values and Pearson correlation coefficient (r), were utilized to analyze the data and determine relationships between variables. Results indicated that local governments exhibited solid institutional and financial capacities, reflecting effective resource management and sound organizational structures. However, information technology capacity, though adequate, was less developed, suggesting the need for improvements in technological infrastructure. The study also revealed full compliance with public service standards, national directives, and regulations, underscoring the cities' commitment to high-quality service delivery and adherence to governance principles. This compliance enhances public accountability, fosters trust, and strengthens local government operations. The findings highlight the strengths and areas for development in BPLS implementation, offering valuable insights for enhancing local government performance.

Keywords: *Local Government Capacity, Institutional and Fiscal Capacity, Information Technology Infrastructure, Compliance with National Directives*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine government has remained steadfast in its commitment to advancing public service delivery, enhancing transparency, and promoting good governance through various strategic initiatives. These efforts align with the goal of ensuring that citizens and businesses benefit from streamlined, efficient, and transparent government processes. One of the key initiatives in this regard is the national simplification of the Business Permits and Licensing System (BPLS), a program aimed at improving the ease of doing business (National Competitive Council, 2016). The importance of such reforms cannot be overstated, as they play a pivotal role in fostering economic growth, attracting investments, and strengthening the country's competitiveness in the global market.

In recent years, the Philippines has made notable progress in the World Bank's Ease of Doing Business (EODB) rankings, moving from 124th in 2018 to 95th in 2019 among 190 economies (Trading Economics, 2023). This improvement signifies the effectiveness of policy reforms in addressing longstanding bureaucratic inefficiencies. However, the challenges remain multifaceted, requiring a concerted effort from legislators, policymakers, local government units (LGUs), and other stakeholders. As Kumar and Kumar (2020) assert, a favorable EODB ranking reflects the efficiency of administrative and legal systems and directly correlates with the investment climate, which spurs economic development. Investments driven by an improved EODB ranking generate a positive feedback loop, fostering sustained growth and progress.

The legislative framework supporting these reforms is robust, spearheaded by Republic Act (RA) 9485, also known as the Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007. This law was designed to enhance the effectiveness of public service delivery by reducing bureaucratic red tape and curbing corruption. Subsequently, the enactment of RA 11032, known as the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018, further strengthened the earlier legislation by institutionalizing mechanisms to streamline government transactions. The Anti-Red Tape Authority (ARTA), established under RA 11032, is tasked with formulating systems, procedures, and policies to improve regulatory management and increase organizational efficiency. This includes providing technical support and advisory services to government agencies and LGUs to ensure compliance with standardized procedures and prompt service delivery (JMC No. 01, 2021).

Moreover, digitalizing government services has emerged as a critical component of these reforms. Adopting e-governance initiatives, such as the e-Business One-Stop Shop (e-BOSS), represents a paradigm shift in how LGUs conduct business permitting and licensing. Under RA 11032, LGUs are mandated to establish fully automated systems that enable the electronic submission of applications, payment of fees, and issuance of permits and clearances. This zero-contact policy enhances efficiency and minimizes opportunities for corruption and other irregularities. The e-BOSS system, as outlined in JMC No. 01 (2021), underscores the importance of integrating technology into governance to achieve greater transparency and accountability.

The broader context of decentralization also significantly shapes the landscape of local governance in the Philippines. The enactment of RA 7160, or the 1991 Local Government Code, and the subsequent issuance of Executive Order No. 138 in 2021, marked a watershed moment in the country's governance framework. These policies mandated the full devolution of functions and responsibilities from national government agencies (NGAs) to LGUs, empowering local governments to take greater control over their resources and decision-making processes. This devolution was intended to enhance service delivery at the grassroots level, enabling LGUs to address the unique needs of their constituents more effectively (Garcia, 2023).

Despite these advancements, significant challenges persist, particularly at the local government level. Reports from the Business Permits and Licensing Offices (BPLO) of San Pablo City, Calamba City, and Santa Rosa City reveal that these LGUs have yet to fully implement automated systems for the issuance of business permits and clearances. The lack of online platforms or courier services for transmitting documents highlights the gap between policy objectives and actual practice (BPLO Reports, 2024). Such inefficiencies undermine the objectives of RA 11032 and the broader agenda of improving the ease of doing business in the Philippines.

The provision of effective public services by LGUs is often hindered by a range of factors, including inadequate funding, limited administrative capacity, and political constraints. As Distor and Khaltar (2022) observe, the inefficiencies in local governance are frequently rooted in poor coordination among government agencies, a lack of standardized procedures, and the competing priorities of local chief executives. These challenges are further compounded by the perception that business registration processes are cumbersome and costly, discouraging small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) from formalizing their operations. For instance, in Lumban, Laguna, only 46% of SMEs possess valid permits, reflecting the barriers that prevent entrepreneurs from complying with regulatory requirements (Adriano, 2023).

Addressing these issues requires a comprehensive approach that considers the institutional, fiscal, and technological capacities of LGUs. Institutional capacity encompasses the organizational structure, human resources, and governance mechanisms that support the implementation and management of BPLS. Fiscal capacity refers to the financial resources available to LGUs to sustain these initiatives, including investments in infrastructure and technology. On the other hand, information technology (IT) capacity pertains to the adequacy of hardware, software, and technical support required for the seamless operation of automated systems.

In addition to assessing LGU capacities, the study also examines their compliance with national directives, public service standards, and regulations. This aspect is critical, as adherence to these standards serves as a benchmark for evaluating the effectiveness of BPLS implementation. The study adopts a quantitative methodology, utilizing surveys to gather data on stakeholder experiences and satisfaction with the system. This approach enables the researchers to provide an objective analysis of the implementation process and identify areas that require targeted interventions.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to contribute to the ongoing discourse on good governance and public service delivery in the Philippines. By focusing on the experiences of San Pablo City, Calamba City, and Santa Rosa City, the researchers aim to provide insights into the factors that influence the successful implementation of BPLS at the local level. The findings are expected to inform policymakers, LGU officials, and other stakeholders on addressing existing gaps and enhancing the efficiency of business permitting processes.

Ultimately, the study seeks to advance the goals of RA 11032 and related policies by promoting a culture of innovation, accountability, and excellence in local governance. The researchers are optimistic that the recommendations from this study will contribute to realizing a more business-friendly environment, thereby supporting economic growth and development in the Philippines.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the extent of implementing the Business Permits and Licensing System (BPLS) in selected cities in Laguna. Specifically, it sought to address the following research questions:

1. What is the level of local government capacity in the three (3) selected cities concerning the Business Permits and Licensing System (BPLS) in terms of:
 - 1.1 Institutional capacity,
 - 1.2 Fiscal capacity, and
 - 1.3 Information technology capacity?
2. What is the level of compliance with national government directives in terms of:
 - 2.1 Public service standards,
 - 2.2 National directives, and
 - 2.3 Regulations?
3. To what extent is the BPLS implemented in the selected cities in Laguna?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the local government capacity and the extent of BPLS implementation in the selected cities in Laguna?
5. Is there a significant relationship between compliance with national government directives and the extent of BPLS implementation in the selected cities in Laguna?
6. What action plan can be proposed to enhance the implementation of the Business Permits and Licensing System in the selected cities in Laguna?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to investigate the relationship between local government capacity and compliance with national government standards concerning the extent of Business Permits and Licensing System (BPLS) implementation in selected cities in Laguna. The research surveyed 54 respondents, specifically employees of the Business Permit and Licensing Office (BPLO)

from three cities: San Pablo (18 respondents), Calamba (11 respondents), and Santa Rosa (25 respondents). These cities were chosen due to their population size and high number of business registrations, and the respondents were selected for their expertise and knowledge of business permitting processes.

A non-probability sampling technique was employed for its practicality and cost-effectiveness, enabling targeted data collection from the identified population. The primary data collection tool was a researcher-made questionnaire comprising sections on informed consent, questions addressing the study's objectives, and items measuring the respondents' perceptions and knowledge. The questionnaire utilized a Likert Scale to measure variables such as local government capacity (institutional, fiscal, and IT capacities), compliance with national standards (public service standards, national directives, and regulations), and the extent of BPLS implementation. Responses were categorized on a four-point scale to capture varying levels of agreement or sentiment.

The questionnaire underwent a rigorous validation process, including review by a statistician, pilot testing in Los Baños, Laguna, and internal consistency testing via Cronbach's alpha, which yielded an acceptable reliability score ($\alpha \geq 0.7$). Following validation, data collection was conducted in the selected cities with formal consent obtained from respondents, ensuring ethical compliance. Respondents were given a week to complete the survey, and the collected data were forwarded to a statistician for analysis.

Ethical considerations were integral to the research process (Gonzales & Villacruel, 2024), adhering to the National Ethical Guidelines for Research Involving Human Participants (2022) by the Philippine Health Research Ethics Board. Informed consent forms were provided and signed by respondents before data collection. The researcher secured approval from the institution's ethics review board and data privacy officer, ensuring adherence to ethical standards and the confidentiality of participant information throughout the study.

Data analysis involved descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, particularly the mean, were used to summarize the respondents' perceptions of local government capacity, compliance levels, and the extent of BPLS implementation. Pearson Correlation Coefficient was employed to determine the strength and direction of relationships between local government capacity and BPLS implementation and between compliance with national government standards and BPLS implementation.

The study's scope was limited to BPLO employees from three selected cities in Laguna, reflecting their perceptions and experiences related to BPLS implementation. As such, the findings may not be generalizable to other regions or sectors. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into the factors influencing BPLS implementation and offers a foundation for enhancing local government processes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Level of local government capacity in terms of Institutional Capacity

Statements	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Interpretation
1. The local government has ordinances in support of BPLS streamlining for effective implementation and enforcement of regulations governing business permits (ex., local revenue code).	3.76	Excellent
2. The local government has established Business One Stop Shop (BOSS) as a frontline service for clients.	3.80	Excellent
3. There is an adequate number of personnel and staff in the office to process and accommodate clients' business permit concerns.	3.52	Excellent
4. Employees are strengthened with development training and seminars related to business permitting systems.	3.37	Excellent
5. The local government's systems and processes are updated on a regular basis to meet changing business needs and regulations.	3.56	Excellent
Overall Mean	3.60	Excellent

The data in Table 1 indicates that the institutional capacity within local government is rated as excellent, with an overall mean value of 3.60. More specifically, the Business One-Stop-Shop (BOSS), which pertains to frontline services dealing with clients, has an excellent capacity with a mean value of 3.80. Additionally, the local government's ordinances supporting BPLS streamlining and the regular updates to the local government's systems and processes to meet changing business needs and regulations were also rated as excellent, with mean values of 3.76 and 3.56, respectively.

This suggests that the institutional capacity of local governments significantly influences the efficiency and effectiveness of the Business Permits and Licensing System (BPLS). A higher institutional capacity, defined by sufficient resources, qualified staff with ongoing development training, and strong infrastructure such as BOSS, can facilitate an efficient, transparent, and user-friendly permit process. This, in turn, creates a more conducive environment for economic growth by reducing bureaucratic hurdles, expediting business application processes, and enhancing applicant satisfaction. Conversely, lower institutional capacity—characterized by resource constraints, insufficient training, and outdated systems—can result in inefficiencies, delays, and a lack of transparency. These issues can undermine public trust, hinder business activity, and stall local economic development. Therefore, investing in strengthening institutional capacity is crucial for streamlining business permit processes and fostering sustainable economic growth.

This finding aligns with the study of Ramos (2022), which examined the municipalities of Taytay and Angono in Rizal Province, both of which have established permanent BOSS facilities. These facilities are designed to reduce corruption in bureaucratic processes and provide citizens a more structured and efficient environment when transacting with the government. Additionally, the study by Alindajao et al. (2023) confirms that One-Stop-Shop (OSS) centers for business licensing offer small businesses faster, simpler, and more cost-effective licensing services by consolidating multiple services in one location. These OSS centers contribute to higher business formalization rates, enhance economic growth, generate government revenue, and create long-term job opportunities. Moreover, OSS facilities are physically designed to minimize direct interaction between business owners and government officials, addressing inefficiencies in license management and reducing the workload on businesses.

Table 2

Level of local government capacity in terms of Fiscal Capacity

Statements	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Interpretation
1. Revenue from business permits substantially contributes to the local government's overall budget.	3.76	Excellent
2. The local government has allocated a budget for BPLS streamlining and automation.	3.69	Excellent
3. The local government may invest in training and development to ensure that its workers possess the skills and knowledge required to manage complicated applications.	3.50	Excellent
4. Inspections, monitoring, and compliance checks can be conducted to ensure that businesses meet the appropriate standards.	3.65	Excellent
5. Revenue from business permits and licenses is efficiently used to create and maintain infrastructure and services that benefit the business community.	3.76	Excellent
Overall Mean	3.67	Excellent

The data from Table 2 revealed that fiscal capacity within local governments is regarded as excellent, with an overall mean value of 3.67. Specifically, the fiscal capacity is demonstrated by (a) revenue from business permits contributing significantly to the local government's overall budget (mean = 3.76), (b) effective utilization of revenue from business permits and licenses to fund infrastructure and services that benefit the business community (mean = 3.76), and (c) budget allocation for the streamlining and automation of the Business Permits and Licensing System (BPLS) (mean = 3.69). These findings indicate that local governments with robust fiscal capacities are better equipped to create and maintain a business-friendly environment through strategic investments in technology, infrastructure, and staff development.

The fiscal capacity of a local government profoundly impacts the effectiveness of its business permitting system. Governments with higher fiscal capacity can invest in advanced technologies, modern infrastructure, and a skilled workforce, enabling quicker permit processing and enhancing the system's overall efficiency. This, in turn, reduces waiting times, lowers administrative costs, and improves satisfaction among business owners and entrepreneurs. A streamlined and efficient permitting process can be a key driver for attracting new businesses, stimulating economic growth, and increasing local tax revenues.

Conversely, limited fiscal capacity can lead to outdated systems, insufficient staffing, and scarce resources, contributing to delays, increased bureaucracy, and frustration among entrepreneurs. Such inefficiencies may hinder business operations, discourage potential investors, and ultimately stunt local economic development. Therefore, it is crucial for local governments to build and strengthen their fiscal capacity to support the establishment of a more efficient, transparent, and business-friendly permitting process.

The importance of fiscal capacity for local government success is supported by studies such as Oñate et al. (2018), which highlight that business license registrations and taxes have long been among the primary sources of income for local governments in the Philippines. Similarly, Ivic et al. (2023) underscore the notion that granting licenses plays a pivotal role in generating revenue for governments, further validating the findings in this study. Strengthening fiscal capacity is not only vital for improving the business permitting system but also for ensuring sustained economic development and prosperity within local jurisdictions.

Table 3

Level of local government capacity in terms of Information Technology Capacity

Statements	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Interpretation
1. There is online platform that facilitates the submission and tracking of permit applications.	3.16	Good
2. Business owners can easily access and use the online system to receive tax order.	3.17	Good
3. The online platform facilitates the online payments/online means of accepting payments.	2.89	Good
4. There is online means or via courier service transmitting business permit and other clearances.	2.35	Fair
5. The system is secure, guaranteeing the confidentiality and integrity of applicant data.	3.33	Excellent
Overall Mean	2.98	Good

The data presented in Table 3 highlights that the information technology (IT) capacity under local government operations is rated as "good," with an overall mean value of 2.98. Specifically, the system demonstrates "excellent" capacity in ensuring the

security, confidentiality, and integrity of applicant data (Mean = 3.33). Meanwhile, it is rated "good" in terms of business owners' ability to easily access and utilize the online system for receiving tax orders (Mean = 3.17) and the availability of an online platform facilitating the submission and tracking of permit applications (Mean = 3.16).

These findings suggest that the effectiveness and user experience of business permitting systems are substantially influenced by local governments' IT capacities. Advanced digital solutions such as online application portals, automated processing, real-time tracking, and electronic or courier-based transmission of permits and clearances can expedite the issuance process. Enhanced IT capacity fosters a business-friendly environment, promoting quicker approvals, reduced errors, and improved accessibility for business owners. Conversely, inadequate IT infrastructure—characterized by outdated technology and inefficient systems—can result in labor-intensive, paper-based workflows, prolonged processing times, and heightened risks of errors and data loss. These inefficiencies can discourage entrepreneurship, hinder local economic growth, and frustrate applicants. Therefore, strengthening IT capacity is essential to creating a streamlined business permit system and sustaining a dynamic business community.

The findings align with the study of Alindajao et al. (2023), which emphasized the public's favorable perceptions of digital business registration services in District 3, Quezon City. Their research underscored how the digitization of business licenses and permits can enhance the accessibility and affordability of licensing services for small businesses. Similarly, the study of Situmorang et al. (2023) demonstrated the effectiveness of the Online Service Management Information System (SIMPONIE) in South Tangerang City, Indonesia. This system enables applicants to register files, undergo verification, and receive approvals through an entirely digital process, significantly benefiting both the public and service providers. Features such as streamlined workflows and enhanced government efficiency illustrate the potential of IT-driven systems to transform licensing services and promote economic development.

Table 4
Compliance with the national government in terms of Public Service Standards

Statements	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Interpretation
1. The local government's Business Permits and Licensing System follows the acceptable timeframes for processing business permit applications.	3.65	Fully Compliant
2. Clear and concise instructions are provided to businesses for the permit application (ex., posting of Citizen's Charter in a conspicuous place).	3.78	Fully Compliant
3. There is a clear understanding and implementation of national licensing laws at the local level (ex., local revenue code).	3.61	Fully Compliant

4. The local government actively seeks feedback from businesses to improve customer service (accomplishment of client feedback form by clients).	3.48	Fully Compliant
5. When it comes to aiding applicants with their permit/license applications, the staff is pleasant and helpful.	3.69	Fully Compliant
Overall Mean	3.64	Fully Compliant

The data from Table 4 reveals that the public service standards related to compliance with national government regulations are fully met, with an overall mean value of 3.64. Specifically, the data shows excellent performance in three key areas: a) the provision of clear and concise instructions to businesses for permit applications (mean value of 3.78); b) the staff's helpfulness and friendliness in assisting applicants with their permit or license applications (mean value of 3.69); and c) adherence to acceptable timeframes for processing business permit applications (mean value of 3.65).

This indicates that the quality of public services provided by local governments is a critical factor influencing the effectiveness and satisfaction with the business permit system. High standards of professionalism, efficiency, and transparency in public service ensure a more responsive and streamlined permit application process. Offering fair treatment, clear communication through feedback mechanisms and the posting of the Citizen's Charter, and meeting timely turnaround expectations, local governments can foster a thriving business environment that attracts and retains companies. In contrast, poor public service standards, characterized by ineffective bureaucracy, poor communication, and a lack of accountability, can lead to delays and frustration for business owners. These deficiencies may erode trust in public institutions, discourage entrepreneurship, and dampen economic activity. Therefore, it is essential to maintain high public service standards to ensure that a business permitting system is equitable, business-friendly, and efficient.

This finding aligns with the study by Perante-Calina and Brillantes (2018), which emphasizes the importance of understanding the Citizen's Charter in promoting public sector reform and improving governance, particularly in ensuring the efficient and effective delivery of public services. Additionally, Gabriel (2018) highlights the role of Republic Act 9485, or the Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007, in reducing bureaucratic inefficiencies, combating corruption, and enforcing penalties for such practices. This legislation mandates public institutions to eliminate "fixing" by complying with ARTA's regulations and prominently displaying the Citizen's Charter, thereby enhancing the transparency and accountability of government services.

Table 5*Compliance with the national government in terms of National Directives*

Statements	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Interpretation
1. Issuance of Barangay Clearance is integrated into the business permit process.	3.82	Fully Compliant
2. There is a local government backroom office at Business One Stop Shop.	3.67	Fully Compliant
3. There are other national agencies at Business One Stop Shop (ex. BFP).	3.54	Fully Compliant
4. The local government has created a TWG on BPLS streamlining.	3.52	Fully Compliant
5. The local government exhibits a commitment to ensuring that the business permits and licensing process adhere to national directives.	3.65	Fully Compliant
Overall Mean	3.64	Fully Compliant

The data from table 5 indicates that the local government's compliance with national directives is fully aligned, with an overall mean value of 3.64. Specifically, the following areas showed full compliance: a) the procedure for obtaining a business permit includes the issuance of a barangay clearance (mean value of 3.82); b) the local government maintains a backroom office at the Business One-Stop Shop (BOSS) (mean value of 3.67); and c) the local government is committed to ensuring that the business permits and licensing process adheres to national directives (mean value of 3.65).

This suggests that the efficiency and consistency of the local business permit system are significantly influenced by adherence to national directives. Enhanced compliance with standard operating procedures—such as the creation of a technical working group on BPLS (Business Permits and Licensing System), along with laws and best practices—promotes uniformity, fairness, and transparency across different areas. Such compliance helps foster a conducive environment for investment and business growth by streamlining the permitting process, reducing corruption, and ensuring a stable economic climate. Conversely, lower compliance with national directives may result in inconsistencies in the permit procedures, increased opportunities for corrupt practices, and an uneven playing field for businesses. These disparities can frustrate entrepreneurs, deter investment, and hinder local economic development. Therefore, strict adherence to national regulations is crucial for creating an efficient, reliable, and business-friendly permitting system. Compliance ensures that the system operates within a standardized framework, promoting fairness and consistency throughout the process.

This is further supported by Firdaus et al. (2023), who examined the licensing procedures for MSME businesses in Pasuruan Regency, East Java, Indonesia. They described the streamlined process facilitated by government agencies, including the One-Stop Integrated Service and Investment Service. These agencies help simplify the

licensing process, allowing businesses to complete all stages—from application to document issuance—through a single door. The government’s role is to support the mayor in managing society, development, and regional government functions. This approach fosters transparency and uniformity in services, improving the quality of licensing and enhancing the effectiveness of public services in supporting the local government’s objectives.

Table 6
Compliance with the national government in terms of Regulations

Statements	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Interpretation
1. Documentary requirements for the application of new and renewal of business permits are clearly defined for clients.	3.72	Fully Compliant
2. For business safety, business owners are informed of adherence to environmental and safety standards.	3.57	Fully Compliant
3. The local government has a composition of Joint Inspection Team (JIT) for the conduct of inspection relative to the operation of the business.	3.52	Fully Compliant
4. The local government has created a fee structure for getting a license and permit.	3.54	Fully Compliant
5. The local government implements appropriate penalties or sanctions for noncompliance with regulatory standards.	3.46	Fully Compliant
Overall Mean	3.56	Fully Compliant

The data from table 6 indicates that the local government’s compliance with national regulations is fully compliant, as evidenced by an overall mean value of 3.56. Specifically, the following areas demonstrated full compliance: a) documentary requirements for the application and renewal of business permits are clearly defined for clients (mean value of 3.72); b) business owners are informed about adherence to environmental and safety standards for business safety (mean value of 3.57); and c) the local government has established a fee structure for obtaining licenses and permits (mean value of 3.54).

These findings highlight that the integrity and functionality of the business permitting system are significantly influenced by regulatory compliance. Strict adherence to regulations ensures that businesses operate within legal frameworks, fostering fair competition, protecting public interests through mechanisms such as penalties for noncompliance, and contributing to overall economic stability. A predictable, transparent, and efficient permitting process can create a reliable business environment that attracts investments and supports long-term growth. Conversely, noncompliance undermines regulatory systems, increasing the likelihood of favoritism, corruption, and inconsistent permit issuance. Such issues can lead to unfair competition, limited opportunities for legitimate businesses, and diminished public confidence in government institutions. Therefore, upholding strict regulatory compliance is essential to creating a just, efficient, and trustworthy permitting system that bolsters both public trust and economic progress.

Adriano (2023) emphasized the importance of regulatory compliance in fostering investor confidence and business growth, citing the case of the embroidery industry in Lumban, Laguna. Legalizing a business and securing proper documentation signal the owner's commitment to its long-term success. Once a business is formally established, entrepreneurs can seek investments or loans to sustain and expand operations. Furthermore, managing legal matters, such as intellectual property registration, is critical in resolving potential conflicts. Obtaining operating licenses and permits is often a prerequisite for businesses, not only in their primary location but also in other areas where they operate.

Similarly, Mardikaningsih and Arifin (2021) highlighted that business formalization involves granting businesses legal entity status and activity permits in compliance with applicable laws. Business licensing serves as a mechanism to establish the legal standing of a business within the community while ensuring that all operations adhere to established rules and regulations.

Table 7

Extent of the Implementation of Business Permits and Licensing System (BPLS)

Statements	$\bar{x}$	Verbal Interpretation
1. Establishes infrastructure for the ease of access to permit application. (ex. presence of Business One Stop Shop)	3.80	Great Extent
2. Observes clarity in the procedures and requirements of business permit processing (ex. Citizen's Charter).	3.72	Great Extent
3. Achieves timeframes to acquire necessary permits.	3.70	Great Extent
4. Provides online business permit application.	3.43	Great Extent
5. Provides online means of payment for business tax, fees, and charges.	3.09	Moderate Extent
6. Provides online means or via courier service transmitting business permit and other clearances.	2.46	Low Extent
7. Involves well-trained staff in administering business permit and licensing system.	3.54	Great Extent
8. Implements customer feedback mechanism.	3.50	Great Extent
9. Observes transparent and reasonable fee structure and requirements for business permits.	3.69	Great Extent
10. Allocates budget for BPLS streamlining and automation.	3.56	Great Extent
11. Undertakes inspections on a regular basis to ensure compliance with permit and license requirements.	3.76	Great Extent
12. Creates Technical Working Group (TWG) on BPLS streamlining.	3.57	Great Extent
13. Integrates clearances to the business permits and licensing system (ex. barangay business clearance)	3.78	Great Extent

14. There is local government's backroom office at Business One Stop Shop.	3.70	Great Extent
15. There are other national agencies at Business One Stop Shop (ex. BFP)	3.63	Great Extent
Overall Mean	3.53	Great Extent

The data from Table 7 indicates that the implementation of the Business Permit and Licensing System (BPLS) is carried out to a great extent, as reflected by an overall mean value of 3.53. Specifically, the following areas demonstrate a great extent of implementation: a) the establishment of infrastructure to ease access to permit applications, such as the presence of a Business One-Stop Shop (BOSS) (mean value of 3.80); b) the integration of clearances into the BPLS, such as barangay business clearances (mean value of 3.78); and c) the conduct of regular inspections to ensure compliance with permit and license requirements (mean value of 3.76).

These findings suggest that the extent of BPLS implementation strongly influences the local business environment and the operational efficiency of the permitting system. Comprehensive implementation ensures compliance with regulations, promotes fairness, minimizes corruption, and enhances administrative efficiency. When BPLS is effectively integrated into government procedures, it streamlines the permit application process—potentially including online services or courier transmission of permits—reduces processing times and increases overall satisfaction among business owners. This, in turn, creates an environment conducive to investment and economic growth. Conversely, inconsistent or partial implementation can result in misunderstandings, inefficiencies, and inequitable treatment of businesses, leading to frustration among business owners and hindering economic progress. Therefore, a fully implemented and consistently applied BPLS is critical for ensuring an equitable, efficient, and business-friendly permitting system.

Ivic et al. (2023) emphasized the significance of e-Government initiatives, such as the establishment of an e-Government Licensing System in Serbia, which provides transactional services to individuals, businesses, and government agencies through online platforms. These systems aim to reduce costs while enhancing effectiveness and efficiency. The United Nations E-Government Survey (2022) noted a 47% increase in the prevalence of online transactional services, such as business licensing, between 2018 and 2020, ranking them as the third most widely used public internet service globally.

Adriano (2023) reinforced the importance of adhering to business registration laws, such as Republic Act 3883, known as the Business Names Law, in Lumban, Laguna. Compliance with these regulations ensures legal business operations in the Philippines, as the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) prohibits the use of unregistered business names.

Table 8

Correlation between the Local Government Capacity and the Extent of the Implementation of Business Permits and Licensing System (BPLS) in Selected Cities in Laguna

		Pearson's <i>r</i>	<i>p</i> - value	Verbal Interpretation
Local Government Capacity	Extent of the Implementation of BPLS	0.428	0.072	Not significant

*Legend: Pearson *r*: Close to +1 indicates a strong positive linear relationship; Close to -1 indicates a strong negative linear relationship; Close to 0 indicates no linear relationship*

p-value: $p < 0.05$ is considered statistically significant; $p > 0.05$ suggests lack of statistical significance

The data presented in Table 8 highlights a computed Pearson correlation coefficient ($r=0.428$), suggesting a moderate positive linear relationship between local government capacity and the extent of implementation of the Business Permit and Licensing System (BPLS) in selected cities in Laguna. This finding implies that as the capacity of local governments improves, there is a corresponding moderate increase in the extent to which the BPLS is implemented within these jurisdictions. However, at the conventional significance level ($\alpha=0.05$), the relationship is not statistically significant ($p=0.072$).

The absence of statistical significance may indicate that the sample size or the variability in the data was insufficient to robustly establish the observed relationship. This underscores the need for further research, potentially with a larger sample or more nuanced analysis, to better understand the interplay between local government capacity and the effective implementation of the BPLS in these cities. Other contributory factors, such as governance practices, stakeholder engagement, and financial resources, may also play a role and warrant exploration.

The findings align with the study by Distor and Khaltar (2022), which emphasized the critical role of capacity-related factors as motivators for Philippine cities to enhance their business registration processes. Their research identified institutional capability, expanded public service experiences, and the development of robust technical infrastructures as key drivers for improving service delivery. This suggests that strengthening local government capacity not only fosters better compliance with regulatory frameworks like BPLS but also contributes to the overall efficiency and responsiveness of public service delivery. Further exploration of these capacity-building elements may provide actionable insights to enhance BPLS implementation and its impact on local economic development.

Table 9

Correlation between Compliance with the National Government and the Extent of the Implementation of Business Permits and Licensing Systems (BPLS) in Selected Cities in Laguna

		Pearson's <i>r</i>	Degree of Correlation	<i>p</i> - value	Verbal Interpretation
Compliance with the National Government	Extent of the Implementation of BPLS	0.505	High Degree	0.039	Significant

*Legend: Pearson *r*: Close to +1 indicates a strong positive linear relationship; Close to -1 indicates a strong negative linear relationship; Close to 0 indicates no linear relationship*

p-value: $p < 0.05$ is considered statistically significant; $p > 0.05$ suggests lack of statistical significance

The data from Table 9 reveals a computed Pearson correlation coefficient ($r=0.505$), indicating a moderate to strong positive linear relationship between compliance with national government directives and the extent of BPLS implementation in selected cities in Laguna. This suggests that higher compliance with national government directives is associated with a moderate increase in the extent of BPLS implementation. The relationship is statistically significant at the traditional threshold of $p=0.05$, as indicated by a p -value of 0.039. These findings support the conclusion that adherence to national government regulations substantially influences the effective implementation of BPLS in the selected cities.

The findings are consistent with the study by Distor and Khaltar (2022), which highlights that following national government guidelines for public service standards improves efficiency. Similarly, Ronyastra and Muhammad (2019) examined the acceptability of the Online Service for Business Permits in Surabaya, Indonesia, and demonstrated how compliance with national directives enhanced the city's reputation as a prototype for other e-government initiatives. Surabaya's Single Window (SSW) platform, which provides various services, including business permits, exemplifies the successful integration of information technology to streamline administrative processes. This initiative aligns with Presidential Instruction No. 3 of 2003, which mandates the use of electronic systems to ensure transparency and efficiency in public services. The Indonesian government's commitment to supporting e-government initiatives across all service areas underscores the broader advantages of adopting such systems, including improved service delivery and administrative efficiency.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the implementation of the Business Permits and Licensing System (BPLS) in three selected cities in Laguna reveals a complex relationship between local government capacity and compliance with national government directives. While areas such as establishing a Business One-Stop Shop (BOSS), integrating barangay

clearance, and providing a Citizen's Charter show strong performance, challenges persist in information technology capacity. Notably, the low compliance with online processing and courier services for business permits and clearances underscores the need for improvement to align with Ease of Doing Business Act requirements.

Statistical analysis further highlights these dynamics. While positive, the relationship between local government capacity and BPLS implementation is not statistically significant, suggesting that other factors may influence BPLS outcomes. In contrast, compliance with national government directives shows a moderate to strong and statistically significant relationship with BPLS implementation, emphasizing its critical role. These findings highlight the need for enhanced IT infrastructure, local administrative capacity, and continued adherence to national standards to ensure a more effective and seamless BPLS implementation in the selected cities.

Recommendations

To enhance the Business Permit and Licensing System (BPLS) in selected cities in Laguna, several recommendations can be proposed. First, local governments in cities like San Pablo, Santa Rosa, and Calamba must strengthen their capacities to promote economic development by improving their business permit and licensing systems. These cities can achieve this by streamlining procedures, implementing digital applications, offering clear guidance to clients, and enhancing administrative efficiency. While the cities already have solid institutional and fiscal capacities, as indicated by the findings, there is a need to enhance information technology (IT) infrastructure, particularly in automating online processes for business permits and clearance transmission. To address this, local governments should adopt integrated digital platforms that improve communication, document management, and data analysis. This can be achieved by investing in robust IT infrastructure, such as online portals and automated workflows, expediting the business permit process and reducing administrative barriers.

In addition, to ensure compliance with national government regulations, local governments must consistently prioritize aligning with national public service standards and legal directives. Routine updates to business processes should account for any changes in legislation or regulatory requirements. Clear communication channels, such as Citizen Charters, can facilitate the exchange of information between business owners and local authorities. Furthermore, joint inspections and technical working groups can help ensure that national regulations are implemented effectively. This coordinated approach will foster a compliant and unified business environment, supporting long-term economic growth. Moreover, regular evaluations of the BPLS are essential to assess areas needing improvement, such as enhancing the availability of online resources or courier services for business permit transmission. Engaging stakeholders and business owners in feedback processes will help identify challenges and ensure the system's effectiveness. By consistently improving the BPLS, the cities in Laguna can create a more favorable environment for entrepreneurship and economic growth while ensuring alignment with national government standards.

Another critical recommendation is the continuous development of local government capacity. A government with the right infrastructure, resources, and expertise is better positioned to implement an efficient BPLS. This includes investing in staff training, adopting new technologies, and optimizing processes. Capacity-building projects will increase transparency and streamline the system, ensuring more consistent and timely service delivery. Lack of resources can lead to inefficiency, which is why investing in building the local government's capacity to manage the BPLS effectively is crucial. Strengthening the relationship between compliance with national government directives and BPLS implementation is essential. Coordination between national and local authorities should be prioritized to ensure uniform application of policies and regulations. By aligning the BPLS with national laws and regulations, local governments can reduce disparities and improve the system's overall effectiveness. To support this, national government capacity-building programs, including training, technical assistance, and advisory support, should be provided to ensure ongoing compliance and efficiency in BPLS operations.

Lastly, enhancing IT capacity is critical to improving the BPLS. An IT infrastructure plan should be developed to enable online submission of business permit applications, clearances, and payments. Digital platforms can reduce financial and time burdens for businesses while promoting transparency and efficiency. A well-designed IT infrastructure will enhance employee productivity and improve customer satisfaction and operational performance. By addressing the technological shortcomings in the BPLS, local governments in Laguna can ensure that business processes are streamlined, secure, and efficient, ultimately benefiting both businesses and local authorities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors of this study affirm their compliance with ethical standards throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose and their rights. Respondents were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any negative consequences. Anonymity was maintained to protect the privacy of all participants, and their well-being was safeguarded at every stage of the research. The authors declare that no conflict of interest influenced the conduct or outcomes of the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and the findings were interpreted impartially based solely on the data collected. The results of this study were used exclusively for research purposes, with a commitment to uphold the integrity of the research process and its outcomes.

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